

Beyond the Norm: Natal Teeth in a Term Male Neonate in Rivers State, Nigeria—a Rare Case Report

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Abstract

This case report sheds light on a challenging obstetric and neonatal scenario involving a 31-year-old gravida 3 para 2 (2 alive) who presented with complications from a traditional birth attendant (TBA) home and subsequently was delivered of a stillbirth with two maxillary incisors in Rivers State, Nigeria. This case underscores the significance of inadequate antenatal care. It also highlights the challenges parents face in decision-making following the management of a stillbirth with natal teeth.

Introduction

The eruption of the lower deciduous incisors is normal at birth in many mammals, except in humans where they are rare [1]. They are slightly more common in females and rare in extremely preterm infants [1,2]. Natal teeth are defined as teeth present at birth, while neonatal teeth are teeth present within 30 days of birth [3,4,8]. Its incidence is reported to be 1:1000 to 1:30,000 [4]. This rare condition presents unique challenges and considerations for both parents and healthcare professionals. Through an examination of this case, we seek to provide a focused analysis of the unique factors influencing health care practices within this specific geographical context, shedding light on this unusual aspect of neonatal oral health.

Case Report

A 31-year-old gravida 3 para 2 (2 alive) with secondary level of education presented with a two-day history of bleeding per vaginam. She had laboured at a traditional birth attendant (TBA) home for three days prior to

presentation. The patient had no formal antenatal care and reported a last normal menstrual period on January 4, 2023. Her estimated delivery date was October 11, 2023, with a gestational age at presentation of 38 weeks and 3 days.

She had no other personal pathological history, no history of intake of medications except vitamins, no family history of systemic illness or ectodermal dysplasia. An emergency caesarean section was performed for placenta previa grade 3b in labour for which the outcome was a male macerated stillbirth. The newborn's measurements included a birth weight of 6kg, occipitofrontal circumference of 39.5cm, length of 54cm, chest circumference of 37cm, mid-upper arm circumference of 13cm, lower limb length of 26cm, foot length of 8cm, and a temperature of 35.3°C. Anal patency was confirmed, and no evident clinical abnormalities were observed.

Oral examination revealed two crowns of teeth in the maxillary anterior region (see Figure 1 and 2), whitish

opaque and exhibiting grade 1 mobility (Miller's classification) categorized as Class 3 according to Helbing's classification (1997) [4]. The lips, gingivae, palate, tongue, floor of the mouth, and buccal mucosa were clinically normal, with no ulceration on the ventral surface of the tongue. A diagnosis of natal teeth was made. Parents did not consent to the extraction, histoanalysis of the teeth, and a post-mortem autopsy due to superstitious beliefs.

Figure 1: Clinical Picture Showing 2 Teeth (Maxillary Incisors; See Arrow)

Note: The image was taken with consent from parents

Figure 2: Clinical Picture Showing the Term Male Stillbirth with Natal Teeth

Note: The image was taken with consent from parents

Figure 3: Clinical Picture Showing the Term Male Stillbirth (Full Image)

Note: The image was taken with consent from parents

Discussion

Natal teeth are three times more common than neonatal teeth [17]. Less than 10% of natal and neonatal teeth are supernumerary, while more than 90% of natal and neonatal teeth are prematurely erupted deciduous series of teeth [3].

They are slightly more common in females and rare in extremely preterm infants [1,2]. The aetiology is largely unknown, nonetheless, several factors have been implicated including hereditary transmission of an autosomal dominant gene [5]. This autosomal dominant gene theory attributes their premature eruption to the superficial position of the tooth germ, possibly influenced by hereditary factors [3,23]. It often manifests with other conditions such as cleft lip and/or palate, craniofacial dysostosis and Pierre-Robin syndrome [1,5,6].

The most commonly affected tooth is the lower primary central incisor (85%), followed by the maxillary incisors (11%) as seen in the index case, mandibular canines and molars (3%) and maxillary canines and molar (3%) [1,4]. The strong predilection for the lower central incisor is consistent with the normal order of eruption of primary deciduous teeth. It usually occurs in pairs as seen in the index patient, more than two are rare, however,

fourteen have been reported [7]. Preservation is advisable if the teeth are stable, yet complications such as Riga-Fede disease (a condition caused by the natal or neonatal tooth rubbing the ventral surface of the tongue during feeding, leading to ulceration) may necessitate conservative or extraction measures. Notably, extraction in newborns is contraindicated due to potential haemorrhage [8].

In Nigeria, natal teeth are relatively unknown, although a few cases have been reported in the literature mostly in South-western Nigeria [13-16, 18]. The paucity of data in this region may be ascribed to role of deeply cultural society where these babies are tagged superstitious and hence cases may be largely underreported [13,19,20]. Amongst the few individual cases reported none was from the south-south region of Nigeria.

The presence of natal/neonatal teeth in the mouth is often associated with certain cultural beliefs/myths. In Malaysian and certain Chinese communities, these teeth are seen as auspicious, while in other societies, they're perceived as ominous signs [22-24]. In regions such as Poland, India, and Africa, children with natal teeth are sometimes regarded as portending misfortune or even seen as monstrous [13,15,29]. Shakespeare's reference to natal teeth in 'King Henry the Sixth' metaphorically suggests readiness to face challenges [17]. Moreover, in England, there existed a belief that having natal teeth guaranteed world conquest [22].

Cultural beliefs, deeply ingrained in the fabric of societies, often determine how individuals perceive health, illness, and medical interventions [25-27]. This case underscores the profound influence of cultural context, where parental decisions were shaped by superstitious beliefs, leading to the deferment of further clinical and radiographic examinations, and procedures such as extraction and histoanalysis

One crucial aspect of the cultural context is its impact on data reporting and collection [24-26]. In cultures where certain medical conditions or practices are considered taboo or stigmatized, there exists a risk of underreporting, leading to a paucity of data [19,20]. The stigma attached to specific health issues may dissuade individuals from seeking medical attention or openly discussing their experiences, creating a skewed representation of healthcare needs within a community [19,24].

Moreover, cultural norms can influence the willingness of individuals to participate in medical research or data collection efforts [27,28]. In instances where communities hold reservations about sharing personal information, researchers may face challenges in gathering comprehensive and accurate data. This underreporting hampers the ability to identify patterns,

understand prevalence rates, and formulate targeted interventions [25,29].

The impact of underreported data extends beyond individual cases to public health planning and policy formulation [25,29,30]. Incomplete or biased data may lead to inadequate resource allocation, undermining the true burden of certain health conditions within a community. This gap in understanding can impede the development of effective health policies, hindering progress towards improving overall healthcare outcomes. A holistic understanding of the cultural context, therefore, is crucial for mitigating data underreporting. Healthcare professionals and researchers must engage with communities in culturally sensitive ways, fostering trust and transparency. Collaborative efforts that respect local beliefs and values can encourage open communication, reducing the stigma associated with certain health issues and facilitating more accurate data collection.

This case in Rivers State, Nigeria serves as a poignant reminder of the need to recognize cultural dynamics and their impact on data reporting. By embracing cultural competency and fostering community engagement, healthcare professionals can not only enhance the accuracy of data but also ensure that interventions are tailored to the unique needs and beliefs of diverse populations. In doing so, we pave the way for a more inclusive, equitable, and effective healthcare system that addresses the complex interplay of culture, decision-making, and data reliability.

Conclusion

This case underscores the critical importance of antenatal care in preventing and managing obstetric complications. The occurrence of natal teeth in the context of a stillbirth adds a layer of complexity, with parental decisions influenced by cultural beliefs hindering necessary medical interventions. The challenges faced in obtaining comprehensive insights into potential underlying issues underscore the need for improved healthcare education, accessibility and cultural sensitivity in maternal and neonatal care in the region. Further research and awareness campaigns are warranted to bridge these gaps and enhance overall healthcare outcomes in similar settings.

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Authors Statement

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